

Review

The Internet of Things (IoT): A Review of Essential Concepts

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Abstract: The Internet of Things, with its acronym (IoT), is a term that has come to stay since 1999, when it was coined by Kevin Ashton. Prior to this new paradigm, only computing devices such as desktops, laptops, tablets, or smartphones could be connected to the internet and exchange information. With the advent of the IoT, the things that make up our physical world have the possibility of being connected to the internet and exchanging information. In this configuration, humans can remotely monitor and control things from anywhere in the world. Consequently, this research article aims at throwing more light on the most essential concepts hovering around the Internet of Things technology. Therefore, this research article will consist of an introduction to IoT; the concept and evolution of IoT; the architecture of IoT comprising the sensing or perception layer, the network layer, the middleware layer, and the application layer; and the research paper will be finalized with some discussions and a conclusion.

Keywords: Internet of Things, IoT Concept, IoT Evolution, IoT Architecture

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Introduction

The purpose of this review article is to simplify the most essential concepts of Internet of Things (IoT) technology. The world of the internet is being revolutionized with the advent of the Internet of Things (IoT), which is a novel paradigm shift encompassing two words, namely "internet" and "things". The concatenation of the internet and things simply implies that the objects referred to as "things" that make up our physical world are constantly able to be connected to the internet and exchange information. Thus, this ability for things to gain access to the internet opens the way for humans to be able to, on the one hand, monitor the state and the environment around these things, and on the other hand, remotely control these things from anywhere in the world. Therefore, the concept of "smart home," "smart city," "smart agriculture," and "smart healthcare" is the resultant effect of "things" being able to gain access to the internet and act automatically.

The Concept of IoT

Kevin Ashton was actually the first to propose the concept of the IoT in 1999. He described the internet of things as a connected object that is uniquely identifiable and embedded with radio-frequency identification (RFID) technology. Nevertheless, the exact definition of the Internet of Things (IoT) is still in the forming process and is subject to the application used [1]. According to [2], the Internet of Things (IoT) was initially described as a worldwide network embedded with the ability of self-configuration. The author added that this dynamic, gigantic worldwide network of things is operating with the guidance of international standards and communication protocols. Indeed, each physical and virtual thing in the IoT has an identity, an attribute, and an interface application. Near Field Communication (NFC) technology can be deployed to uniquely identify IoT connected devices [3]. Therefore, the combination of the words "Internet of Things" means a global interconnection of objects managed by sensors, actuators, networks, middleware, and monitoring applications, which might be referred to as the novel paradigm of information and communication technology. Despite differing perspectives on the definition of IoT technology, broad discussion has occurred, and corresponding technologies have been rapidly developed by various institutions [4]. Intelligent sensing and wireless communication techniques, in particular, have become integral to the IoT, and new challenges and research opportunities have emerged [5]. Discussions on IoT enabling technologies, their challenges, potential markets, and their implications have been reached by the International Telecommunication Union [6]. Radio Frequency Identification (RFID) is the enabling technology that initiated the IoT, and it is progressively used in logistics, retail, pharmaceutical production, and different industries [7, 8]. Wireless sensors have considerably extended the capability of things, making them intelligent and autonomous. Nowadays, a plethora of technologies are harnessed in IoT, including wireless sensor networks (WSNs), intelligent sensing, Near Field Communication (NFC), Radio Frequency Identification (RFID), low energy wireless communications, barcodes, and so on [9, 10]. It's of paramount importance to note that the evolution of the aforementioned technologies conveys novel techniques to IoT technology. Therefore, the concept of IoT actually describes a new form of the internet whereby the objects that make up our physical world are embedded with the capability of being accessed and identified through the internet. Definitions of IoT vary depending on the technology deployed for implementation. Nevertheless, the fundamental concept of the Internet of Things is the ability of objects to be uniquely identifiable. Thus, with the advent of the IoT, everything has the ability to exchange data and, if necessary, process data according to predefined schemes.

The Evolution of IoT

It is worth noting that the concept of interconnecting systems and physical objects has in the past been a very great subject of interest for those who have a growing appetite for innovation. Consequently, a wide variety of innovations have seen the light of day. Radio Frequency Identification (RFID) technology is known across the board as the device used by technology innovators to wirelessly identify objects and people using radio waves. So, even though in the early days of technology the word "IoT" was not pronounced, the idea of interconnecting systems geographically distant so that they could communicate with each other was already conceived and even implemented. The first person who actually coined the concept of IoT was Kevin Ashton in 1999, when he made use of RFID to link physical objects through radio waves. His vision was a world where things would be uniquely identifiable through the internet, with the ability to collect, process, record, analyse, and present information through computers without human intervention. So, the history of the IoT is inextricably linked to RFID as the enabling technology and Kevin Ashton as the founding father. A comprehensible recapitulation of the Internet of Things timeline evolution is illustrated in fig.1 below.

Fig. 1: Internet of Things Timeline Evolution
(Source: Techahead, 2022)

IoT Architecture

It is worth noting that there is no one-size-fits-all IoT architecture designed to suit all applications. There is architectural diversity because of the plethora of IoT applications in existence, with new ones emerging day by day. As a consequence, varieties of architecture have emerged over the years from scholars. Some scholars advocate for an IoT architecture of three layers, namely: perception, network and application layer [11]; some for four layers comprising sensing, network, middleware and application layer [12]; while others advocate for one of five layers made up of perception, transmission, middleware, application and business layer [13].

Fig. 2: Three-layer IoT architecture
(Source: Yousuf et al., 2015)

Fig. 3: Four-layer IoT architecture
(Source: Hassija et al., 2019)

Fig. 4: Five-layer IoT architecture
(Source: Xuyang et al., 2016)

The International Telecommunications Union (ITU) recommends an IoT reference model comprising four layers: application layer, service support, application support layer, network layer, and device layer. This model incorporates additional features such as security capabilities and management capabilities [14].

Fig. 5: IoT Reference Model
(Source: ITU, 2012)

Perception layer

The IoT perception layer provides a physical meaning to each device. It comprises IR sensors, RFID tags and other networks that have the ability to sense humidity, temperature, location and speed of devices. This layer collects and gathers data from devices through sensors. It converts collected data into useful, informative digital signals. These signals are given to the network layer for further processing [15] (Goyal et al., 2021). According to the International Telecommunication Union [14], the perception layer is referred to as the device layer and it is logically

categorised into two capabilities, namely: device capability and gateway capability. Device capability implies the ability of devices to gather and upload information directly to the communication network and can equally receive commands directly from the communication network without making use of gateway capabilities. Notwithstanding, devices have the ability to indirectly gather and upload information to the communication network through gateway capabilities, and can receive commands from gateway capabilities. The device layer has the ability to do ad-hoc networking, with sleeping and waking up capabilities to save energy. The gateway capabilities of the device layer can support multiple interfaces like Bluetooth, ZigBee, Wi-Fi, and Controller Area Network [14]. Gateway capabilities can communicate via second or third generation (2G or 3G) networks, Public Switched Telephone Networks (PSTN), Long-Term Evolution Networks (LTE), Ethernet, or Digital Subscriber Line (DSL). Another gateway capability of the device layer of the ITU IoT reference model is that of protocol conversion, which is needed when different device layer protocols are used for communication at the device layer (e.g. Bluetooth and ZigBee technology protocols). Gateway capabilities are also needed when different protocols are used during communication between the device layer and the network layer (e.g. 3G technology protocol at the network layer and ZigBee technology protocol at the device layer).

Table 1: Elements of the perception layer

Element	Function
Sensor	Collects information about the environment
Actuator	Puts ON and OFF a device automatically
RFID	Uses radio waves to uniquely identify, monitor and track tagged objects
QR Code Reader	Track product information in a supply chain
Barcode Reader	Reads and decodes product information printed on barcodes
IP Camera with inbuilt microphone	Monitors access by capturing image and sound in real-time
Robotic arm	Performs mechanical tasks automatically

Network Layer

The network layer receives digital signals carrying useful information from the perception layer. It sends this information received to processing systems for processing and analysis. It uses various mediums of transmission such as Bluetooth, GSM, Wi-Fi, ZigBee, WiMaX, 4G, and 5G. It uses protocols such as MQTT, DDS, IPv4 and IPv6 [15]. According to [14], the network layer is embedded with networking capabilities and transport capabilities. Network capabilities denote the provision of relevant control functions of network connectivity, such as authentication or mobility management, transport resource control functions, access, authorization, and accounting. Transport capabilities denote the provision of connectivity for the transport of IoT services as well as the transportation of IoT control and management information.

Table 2: Elements of the network layer

Element	Function
WiMAX	Deliver connections to networks based on the IEEE 802.16 family of standards.
Wi-Fi	Creates small networks that enable nearby digital devices to exchange information through radio waves. It is governed by the IEEE 802.11 family of standards. It uses the unlicensed 2.4GHz band.
3G, 4G and 5G Cellular	Enables mobile communication
LoRaWAN	Connects low-powered devices to the internet for long range wireless communication. Can cover up to 10Kilometers.
Bluetooth	Builds personal area networks where data could be exchanged wirelessly over a short distance. Operates in the free 2.402 GHz to 2.48 GHz Industrial, Scientific and Medical (ISM) radio unlicensed range. Operates up to 10 metres range.
ZigBee	Creates a low-power radio wireless IoT personal area network. Guided by IEEE 802.15.4 standard and operates in 2.4GH, 900MH and 868MH Industrial, Scientific and Medical (ISM) unlicensed bands.

Middleware layer

This layer processes data received from sensors. It utilises cloud computing, allowing access to its database directly for storage of necessary data. Data collected is processed and analysed using smart processors and algorithms. An automatic action is initiated based on processed results and analysis [15]. The service support and application support layers do the job of the middleware layer [14]. This layer is embedded with generic support capabilities and specific support capabilities. The former refers to capabilities used by different IoT applications like data processing and storage. The latter refers to particular capabilities that manage the requirements of diverse applications.

Table 3: Elements of the middleware layer

Element	Function
IoT cloud platforms such as Amazon web services, Oracle cloud, Microsoft azure, Google cloud, Salesforce etc.	They enable storage over the internet, service over the internet and applications over the internet.

Application Layer

The application layer realizes different IoT applications based on processed data and information. The application layer is useful in IoT network development. IoT based applications are smart wearable devices, healthcare, patient monitoring, homes, vehicles, agriculture, weather forecasting, and smart cities [15]. According to the International Telecommunication Union [14], the application layer simply refers to the various sectors where IoT could be applied.

Table 4: Elements of the application layer

Element	Description
Agriculture	Farmers can remotely monitor the condition of the soil and irrigation performed automatically thanks to IoT sensors and actuators. This constitutes the concept of smart agriculture.
Health	Doctors can remotely monitor patient's conditions. Thus, the concept of smart healthcare.
Traffic monitoring	IoT eases the management of vehicles in large cities. Thus, the concept of smart cities.
Home	Homeowners have the ability to remotely monitor and control home appliances through the internet using smartphones.

Discussion

Before the birth of IoT technology, the idea of interconnecting machines for the purpose of communication had been conceived and implemented. Most scholars have demonstrated that conventional IoT architecture is embedded with three layers, namely: the perception layer, the network layer, and the application layer. Nevertheless, there are a plethora of IoT architectures with additional layers proposed by other scholars. These architectures' layers include a perception layer, a network layer, a middleware layer, a processing layer, a service support and application support layer, an application layer, and a business layer. The International Telecommunication Union [14], recommends additional capabilities for IoT architectures, which are: management capabilities (generic and specific management capabilities), and security capabilities (generic and specific security capabilities). Management capabilities refer to performance management, configuration management, accounting management, fault management, and security management. Generic management capabilities in the Internet of Things refer to the management of devices (i.e., remotely activating and de-activating devices; management of device working status; updating firmware and software; and diagnostics); traffic and congestion management (i.e. network overflow detection and resource reservation for life-critical and time-critical data flows); and local network topology management. Specific management capabilities refer to the management of application-specific requirements, such as the monitoring requirements for smart grid power transmission lines. Generic security capabilities are quite independent of applications. These capabilities at the device layer include: authorization, authentication, access control, device integrity validation, data integrity protection, and confidentiality. At the level of the network layer, the capabilities include: authorization, authentication, signalling integrity protection, and signaling data confidentiality. At the level of the application layer, the capabilities include: authentication authorization, data confidentiality, privacy protection, integrity protection, security audit, and anti-virus. Specific security management capabilities refer to application-specific requirements, such as security requirements and mobile payment.

Conclusion

The purpose of this review article was to provide a comprehensible presentation of the most essential concepts of IoT, with a focus on the concept and evolution of IoT, alongside the architecture of IoT. Therefore, this article covered the most essential concepts of IoT: an introduction to IoT; the concept and evolution of IoT; and the architecture of IoT

with three, four, or five layers depending on the authors. It can therefore be concluded that before the advent of IoT, the idea of machines being interconnected and exchanging information had already seen the light of day. Also, even though some scholars advocate for an IoT architecture of four or five layers, the conventional architecture advocated by most scholars is that of three layers, namely: the perception layer, the network layer, and the application layer.

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